

USE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING NATURAL GEOGRAPHY OF CONTINENTS AND OCEANS

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Annotation. The design, development and widespread use of electronic geography textbooks in the educational process is becoming an urgent issue, as they are widely used in the field of education. Recently, various types of electronic educational publications have been created, which include from simple hypertext textbooks to complex distance learning systems.

Key words. Informative approach, electronic textbooks, information technologies, educational computer programs, interactive maps.

Introduction. The widespread use of new information technologies, the computerization of society, the development of new means of communication have led to significant changes in the field of education. In recent years, we have become more and more convinced that almost all relationships that exist in nature are informational in nature. The use of an informational approach in teaching the natural geography of continents and oceans in higher education institutions provides an unlimited opportunity to expand the concepts of teaching methods, to use the methods of organizing the student's educational activities and selecting them at different stages of the information process.

Main part. At the initial stage, in various ways, the preparation and subsequent delivery of information on the natural geography of continents and oceans, and the effects that increase the student's ability to receive information to perceive the information, are prioritized. Analysis, better assimilation of all concepts, as well as the development of thinking are directly related to tasks and commands that require students to perform actions in non-standard situations, arranged in a logical

sequence. In our science, in a logical sequence, first the continent of Africa, then the continents of Australia, Antarctica, South America, North America, Eurasia, and then the knowledge, information, concepts, place names, information sources related to the Pacific, Atlantic, Indian and Arctic Oceans. developed using This process contributes to the purposeful processing of information and the formation of necessary skills and behaviors in students.

Information is a means of transferring knowledge and concepts in a communicative form.

According to I. O. Pashchenko, the process of informational approach in education includes:

- providing educational institutions with computers and software;
- connection and work with regional, national and international educational networks through high-speed channels, use of the global Internet network;
- creation and posting of educational information resources on the Internet, integration of various databases at the regional and state level:
 - educational portals of higher education, official sites of each educational institution, resources on various topics, methodological sites, electronic libraries, information-search and analytical systems, etc.;
 - development, validation, then testing and implementation of selected training programs, including digital learning resources;
 - supporting the formation of information culture in every participant of the educational process, be it an employee, teacher, student or their parents, as well as providing information technology tools in all educational institutions;
 - targeted continuous training of information technologies for the teacher according to a certain system (courses, Express-courses, mini-seminars, regular seminars, conferences, competitions, solving pedagogical problems, system of individual consultations, work of problematic and creative groups, professional communication, etc.).

Due to the use of information technologies in the educational process, the effectiveness of the educational process increases significantly. The effectiveness of using informational educational technologies in teaching the natural geography of continents and oceans is as follows:

- information is presented in different forms;
- high visibility; ability to model processes;
- use by the whole team in the organization of project - research works;
- differentiated approach to each work of students, regardless of their level of preparation, cognitive interests, etc.;
- operational control and teacher support.

The use of information technologies in educational institutions significantly facilitates students' access to educational information, as well as opens great opportunities for changing educational activities, individualizing and differentiating them. The student becomes an active and equal participant in the learning process.

Educational computer programs. These programs allow the teacher to present the material in such a way that the most important concepts are presented in high-quality illustrations for various topics. Initially, each program is developed and created based on the combination of verbal-logical and figurative thinking mechanisms to stimulate the student's cognitive activity. For example, the Globus v2.0 program is designed to test knowledge about the geographical map of the world. Google Earth is a 3D mapping program that includes several features for virtual exploration of the planet earth. A set of programs for creating maps, analyzing data, editing and designing by downloading ArcGIS. Global Mapper is a GIS data analysis and processing program.

Modern multimedia computer programs and telecommunication technologies. Multimedia is a computer technology that combines and processes texts, graphics, audio and video data, various animations and computer models. With the help of these programs and technologies, various sources of information are available to students. Electronic hypertext textbooks, educational sites, distance learning systems

are designed to significantly increase the effectiveness of cognitive and independent development.

The electronic textbook contains text, digital, speech, graphic, musical, video, photo information. An electronic textbook is a teaching tool designed for the use of educational methods based on computer technologies, and it can be used for independent education and effective mastering of educational materials. In the electronic textbook, the educational materials of the subject are used in an interactive way for the student, psychological and pedagogical aspects, modern information technologies, audio and video animations are appropriately used.

Electronic textbooks can be divided into the following types:

- electronic version of the text;
- hypertext electronic version of the book;
- a textbook with graphs, tables, pictures and hypertexts;
- a textbook with animation, sound, graphics, tables, pictures and hypertext;
- textbooks with animation, sound, graphics, tables, pictures, hypertext and test systems.

Initially, electronic textbooks had a very simple appearance, but now they are enriched with visual tools that affect the human psyche. Various animation and video files can be added to such tools. Initially, these opportunities did not exist. Over time, the development of Flash, 3D Max programs made the preparation of electronic textbooks more meaningful and the content more understandable to the user. All this allows rapid exchange and acquisition of information electronically. Presentation of educational material on natural geography of continents and oceans in the form of animations in an electronic presentation facilitates understanding of the subject and increases visibility.

First of all, it is necessary to know how e-textbooks affect the quality of lessons. The following advantages of electronic textbooks compared to traditional methods can be cited:

1. Form of presentation of educational information.

2. Ability to search for necessary information.
3. Availability of methods of controlling the level of acquired knowledge.
4. Availability of feedback with the teacher.

Intellectual control program: control programs (with educational elements, game, modeling with control elements, etc.) are developed taking into account the recommendations of pedagogical practice.

An electronic reference is a virtual system designed for informational training, covering the full or partial volume of the educational process. There are many geography reference books: Geography Final Exam Preparation Guide. "Encyclopedia around the world" and others.

Interactive maps are geography teaching tools that significantly expand the possibilities of presenting the studied material. Using interactive maps in the lessons of the natural geography of continents and oceans, the teacher creates visual non-standard images. Advantages and types of working with an interactive map:

- the ability to display individual regions for more detailed study (some maps have added additional illustrative and textual materials related to the region);
- show certain annotations and conditional symbols on the map that are needed only in a certain lesson; it is possible to draw drawings on the map and make various notes.

- real work with card layers;
- use of additional materials;

The importance of electronic maps increases due to the drawing function. There is an opportunity to draw a certain object or objects on the card that students should pay special attention to. The electronic map opens up unlimited opportunities for the teacher and students to explore the area at different stages of learning geography.

The issue of the use of computer technologies in the process of teaching natural geography of continents and oceans is extremely multifaceted, and its three main directions are distinguished: first, it is the direct use of information technologies in geography lessons. application, which is most often used in practical training;

secondly, the use of information technologies to organize extracurricular activities of students; thirdly, information technologies are aimed at providing knowledge-oriented free time (such as games that help students' mental development, electronic dictionaries).

Conclusion. The use of computer technologies is one of the most important components of the development of natural geography of continents and oceans as a science and educational subject. Computer technology advances the ideas of software education, discovers the newest and untested technological options for teaching, and they realize the enormous potential of modern computers and telecommunications. Computer technology of teaching is preparation of information with the help of a computer and conveying it to the student. But this process is quite complicated, it requires both the teacher and the students to be computer literate, that is, to know how to use technical and software tools to obtain, process or create the required amount of information. Improving the computer literacy of students, using modern educational information technology in the school provides fundamentally new opportunities to improve the pedagogical process and, on this basis, to raise the general education level of the young generation.

References

1. Беспалько В.П. Образование и обучение с участием компьютеров (педагогика третьего тысячелетия). – М.: Издательство Московского психолого – социального института; «МОДЕК», 2002. – 352 с.
2. Душина И. В., Таможняя Е.А., Путятин В.Б. Методика и технология обучения географии: Пособие для учителей и студентов пед. институтов и университетов. – М.: Издательство «Астрель»: , 2002. – 203с.
3. <http://kompy.info/zamonaviy-informatika-va-axborot-texnologiyalari-on-line-darsl.html?page=6>